

Effect of Ageing on Coagulation Constants of Stannic Hydroxide Sol

Mukhtar Singh and O. P. Bansal

The constants, 'a', 'm' and 'n' of the equation¹, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot l/t}{n + l/t}$, depend on the stability of the sol and as the stability changes on ageing, these constants obviously will no longer have the same value. Thus, an attempt has been made to study the effect of ageing on the above constants for dialysed stannic hydroxide sol using NaCl and KCl as coagulating electrolytes.

Stannic hydroxide sol was prepared and dialysed². The time of coagulation of the sol was determined, over a number of days, by light extinction method and the constants (a, m and n) were found graphically³.

TABLE I

Values of the constants a, m and n

Period of ageing (days)	Concentration of the sol = 9.50 g. SnO ₂ /litre							
	KCl				NaCl			
	a (mM/l)	m (mM/l)	(a+m) (mM/l)	n (min ⁻¹)	a (mM/l)	m (mM/l)	(a+m) (mM/l)	n (min ⁻¹)
0	60.0	32.26	92.26	0.0460	40.0	20.83	60.83	0.0143
15	60.0	28.60	88.60	0.0370	40.0	20.00	60.00	0.0140
30	55.0	25.00	80.00	0.0250	35.0	22.72	57.72	0.0112
60	50.0	26.60	76.60	0.0185	30.0	25.64	55.64	0.0090
90	45.0	25.60	70.60	0.0143	25.0	22.50	47.50	0.0082
105	40.0	26.40	66.40	0.0152	20.0	23.26	43.26	0.0078

If l/t is made large as compared to n , the equation, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot l/t}{n + l/t}$, takes up the form, $C = a + m$. This means that 'm' is the excess of the electrolyte that should be added above the critical stability concentration, 'a' in order to cause immediate coagulation of the sol. It may be said that at, $C = a + m$, the region of slow coagulation merges into that of

1. A. K., Bhattacharya, and Ram Kumar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 179, & 638; 1952, **29**, 687 & 759; A. K. Bhattacharya, Ram Kumar and Amal K. Bhattacharya, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, **10**, 551.
2. M. Singh and O. P. Bansal, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 787.
3. A. K. Bhattacharya, Arvind Kumar and Amal Kumar, *Agra Univ. J. Res. Sci.*, 1963, **12**, 101; A. K. Bhattacharya, and Amal K. Bhattacharya, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1956, **11**, 124.

rapid coagulation. From the table, it is evident that the value of $(a+m)$ decreases with the ageing of the sol indicating that the region of slow coagulation merges into that of rapid coagulation earlier in the aged sol. From this, it appears that the ageing results in decreasing the stability of the sol. Ageing results in aggregation of the particles as is evidenced by the decrease in the values of 'n' and this aggregation renders the sol unstable.

Thanks are due to Dr. A. K. Bhattacharya, and Dr. A. Kumar for their valuable suggestions in this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

Received, October 23, 1967.